

PROBLEM SOLVING METHODS TO IMPROVE UNDERSTANDING OF LEARNING SOCIAL SUBJECT MATTER FOR STUDENTS OF VII OF SMP NEGERI 2 TIGARAKSA, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

Based on the subjects of social sciences, the students are directed, guided, and helped to become Indonesian citizens and to be effective world citizens. To develop these capabilities, it requires the necessary competence of teachers in delivering learning. Skills teachers in planning lessons need to take into account and relate to the methods that will be used in learning. Problem solving method is a way of solving problems based on data or information which is accurate to obtain a conclusion. This research was implemented to improve the process by applying certain methods. As a matter of fact, the procedure is done through action planning, action, observation and reflection. The research cycle lasted a few times until the learning objectives achieved the social knowledge material, in this case, the subject of Natural Resources. The results showed, in the first cycle, the writer got the average value of the subject of the Natural Resources subject of 38 students at 5.63, at the second cycle was 6.92, while the third cycle was 7.53. There was an improvement of results from the first cycle to the second cycle was 23%, while, the second cycle to the third cycle of 9%. Overall, during the treatment performed by three cycles, there was an increase of learning outcomes through method of solving the problem by 34%.

Keywords: developing ability, teachers' competence, problem solving

1. Introduction

Social subject matter becomes one of the subjects in the curriculum Competency Based ranging from elementary school to high school (SMP) or equivalent. The scope of Social

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Sciences subjects in junior high school are stated as follows: social and cultural systems, people, places and the environment, economic behavior and well-being, sustainability and certain changes and system state and nation. In social science subjects, students are directed, guided, and helped to become Indonesian citizens and effective world citizens (Maryani and Syamsudin, 2009). Therefore, the social sciences are designed to build and reflect the ability of students in public life is always changing and evolving (Laila, Haryono, and Sumarni, 2016). To develop these capabilities, one needs to improve the competence of teachers in delivering learning.

In delivering learning, teachers need to have a certain competence before delivering teaching materials. One of the necessary competences is possessed by the teachers' capabilities in organizing learning materials (Kheruniah, 2013). To perform these tasks, teachers should have the skills in planning learning according to the characteristics of teaching materials and student characteristics. Skills teachers in planning lessons need to pay attention to the methods that will be used in learning. In this case, there are several kinds of methods to convey the subjects of Social Sciences, including problem-solving methods.

Problem solving method is a way of solving problems based on data or information that is accurate to obtain a conclusion (Kizilirmark, Wiegmann, Klavehn, 2016). Meanwhile, problem solving is a process of mental and intellectual in finding a problem and solves it based on the data. According Hamalik (1993) states troubleshooting methods can give learners the opportunity to actively participate in the study, seek and find their own information or data to be processed into the concepts, theories or conclusions. The use of problem-solving methods in teaching social studies, are expected to guide, explore and communicate data to a conclusion (Dogru, 2008). Having a success in delivering learning social studies teacher with a problem-solving method, assumed it would have implications for the improvement of learning outcomes.

To be successful as a learning process, teachers need to consider the suitability of the method with the material. The discrepancy between the two, it assumed that it will have implications on learning outcomes. Less optimal teacher's creativity in finding various methods in solving problems faced by students are assumed to have implications for the quality of the process. Selection of appropriate methods in processing an assumed learning will affect the success of learning in question. Based on researchers' observation in the field, shows the results of social studies including unsatisfactory category. It is thus necessary an effort to improve results in line with expectations. Based on the observation of the results of social studies in Class VII SMP Negeri 2 Tigaraksa average rating of 3.73, students whose grades six under six as much

as 84.21% while the above as much as 13.16%. Based on these data, the treatment is done with the aim to improve the understanding of students in social subject.

2. Method

The researcher used a qualitative research approach Action Research. The aim of doing the research, she classified the problems of learning and in a particular class (Robinson and Walters, 2016). This study was done to improve the process by applying certain methods (Schofield, 2012). Broadly speaking, the procedure is done through action planning, action, observation and reflection. The study was conducted in classes VII-D SMP Negeri 2 Tigaraksa the school year 2016/2017 the number of students as many as 38 people. The procedure used in this study with the system cycle spiral-shaped reflection. Research cycle lasted a few times until the learning objectives achieved social subject matter, in this case the subject of Natural Resources.

She put forward the implementation of the actions carried out with the following steps: planning the teaching was done by selecting a topic that is appropriate for solving the problem. The implementation started with a perception or reference questions related to the subject to be presented. This is done to determine the ability of the students early, before using the method of problem solving. The steps of solving the problem were stated as follows:

1. Gathering the data, the students were managed to collect the necessary data through learning resources and media, as well as the results of activities and exchange ideas with other group members.
2. Analyzing the data, the data have been analyzed based on the students' thinking skills.
3. Developing and formulating hypotheses, data have been analyzed, further hypothesized in the form of provisional estimates as an alternative solution.
4. Assessing hypotheses, conjectures as a temporary answer is then considered its causes and consequences.
5. Processing the data, then, data have been analyzed and compiled in the form of the hypothesis, then reprocessed in order to more clearly toward a solution.
6. Conducting the experiment, once solved, and then tested truth that really the right answer to solve the problem.
7. Drawing conclusions, after each group to report the results of the answers on the Student Worksheet, eventually it can be deduced last of the ones above.

3. Result and Discussion

At the time of the learning process, the activities and engagement of learners were still not built, because at that time there were still many students who answered questions of teachers simultaneously, there was also the unfocussed answer and not on target, but through the guidance of teachers, all can overcome. In general, all learners can follow the learning and use the time to learn well. Although sometimes there are learners who noisier, but everything is still within reasonable limits. SDA subject of learning outcomes in class VII-D is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The result of learning of natural resources subject matter for class VII-D

In the first cycle of 38 students on the subject of the natural resource matter has a value range of 3-6 after treatment with the troubleshooting methods in the second cycle changes increase. But there is one student who did not take the test and 2 students with a value of 4. This became the basis for treatment in the third cycle, the cycle of the changes increase the value of the range of scores 4-9. Generally, during problem solving methods average values of each cycle occur modest of progress. To increase the value of each cycle, it was shown in Figure 2. Based on the Figure, in the first cycle the average value the subject of the Natural Resource subject of 38 students at 5.63, in the second cycle of 6.92, while the third cycle of 7.53. The increased of results of learning from the first cycle to the second cycle of 23%, while from the second cycle to the third cycle of 9%. Overall, during the treatment performed by the researcher for three cycles, there was an increase learning outcomes by method of solving the problem by 34%.

Figure 2: The average of natural resources discussion

The existence of several students who are lacking in improving learning outcomes natural resources subject matter should be examined comprehensively from the answers that a student made. The results obtained, the students' answers only to the extent the final answer, no reasons were supposed to put forward. Researchers concluded, learners do not understand the meaning of questions. Thus, this method of problem solving, the students would need to be trained to avoid pragmatic mindset. With the method of problem solving, students are encouraged to think critically to find answers or settlement is expected.

4. Conclusion

Social subject learning through the method of problem solving can be applied to the students, because the impact of the use of this method is very advantageous, among them students become more critical in responding to any problems that arise, students can train the ability to communicate, improve the ability to dig his own knowledge, and to improve the taste solidarity, thus improving learning achievement. Based on the analysis of students' answers, then there are some conclusions as stated as follows:

1. Students are less careful in reading the sentence contained in the problem, so that students get difficulties to understand the question.
2. Some students did not fill in a matter which is considered difficult.
3. The answer given by the student does not lead to the desired answer.
4. In general, students do not re-examine the results of the answers he had written.

5. Lacking of collection of the vocabulary of the students, it caused students are not able to describe the answer which it is intended.

From the above analysis, it can be concluded that in general students are not able to get the meaning of the questions presented. So, the researcher tried to apply the method of problem solving as one of the methods that are considered to help improve students' skills in social studies learning. Because, basically, the researcher put forward the problem solving method based on the accurate and real data.

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